

Greyia sutherlandii Glossy Bottlebrush

© D. Berger

Group: Eudicot

Size: 0.5 - 8 m (height)

Distribution:

The Glossy Bottlebrush is endemic to South Africa, occurring in Mpumalanga and KwaZulu-Natal. It typically grows on rocky slopes, cliff faces, and open grassland in montane habitats

Importance:

The bottlebrush, an endemic plant of montane regions, plays a key role in ecosystem services. Rich in flavonoids, it shows promising anti-tyrosinase activity with potential medicinal benefits for skin conditions. Its striking flowers add horticultural appeal, making it both a functional and ornamental asset.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 31.02 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 10.31 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Genome Length: 0.18 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.6% [Single: 85.9%, Duplicated: 13.7%]

Assembly N50: 3.295 kilobases

Contig number: 307

Sample Contributor contact details:

Prof. Dave Berger

University of Pretoria

dave.berger@fabi.up.ac.za